

APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND PROBIOTICS FOR DEACTIVATION OF AFLATOXIN IN FOOD PRODUCTS. REVIEW

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Abstract

The article provides a detailed review of recent studies examining the role of probiotics in the degradation of aflatoxins, highly toxic compounds in food that pose significant health risks. Regulatory standards for aflatoxin levels in foodstuffs have been established to protect public health. Various methods—chemical, physical, and biological—have been developed for decontaminating and detoxifying aflatoxins. Among biological methods, probiotics have shown substantial potential in decontaminating aflatoxins. Studies indicate that probiotics can reduce the bioavailability of aflatoxins through adsorption or binding to their cell walls, facilitating their excretion from the body. The extent of aflatoxin absorption by probiotics is influenced by several factors, including the complexity of the food matrix. Emerging food processing technologies also offer promising results in aflatoxin degradation. Combining these emerging technologies with probiotics can enhance the overall effectiveness of decontamination efforts. In addition, environmental factors influenced by climate change could affect aflatoxin production, necessitating advanced decontamination techniques. The reviewed studies underscore the importance of optimizing probiotic strains and their conditions of use to maximize their effectiveness in aflatoxin degradation, as well as exploring the potential of combining these biological methods with novel technological approaches.

Keywords: mycotoxin, aflatoxins, deactivation, probiotic bacteria, binding, adsorption, fermentation, ultrasound

Introduction

In the past decade, food products contaminated by mycotoxins have been a critical problem regarding global food safety [1]. These toxins are fungi secondary metabolites produced by *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Alternaria* [2]. More than 400 compounds have been identified and reported as mycotoxins, such as aflatoxins, zearalenone, ochratoxins, patulin, fumonisins and deoxynivalenol. Aflatoxins (AFs) are the most poisonous of these produced by some toxigenic species of *Aspergillus*, mainly by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* [3].

AFs contaminate different food commodities such as cereals, nuts and spices to damage human and animal health [4]. AF (AFM1) has also been isolated from milk and milk products resulting from consuming contaminated animal feed [5]. The class of aflatoxin contains more than twenty secondary metabolites; the principal is aflatoxin B1, B2, G1 and G2 (AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, AFG2) [6]. The degree of toxicity varies. AFB1 is the most toxic for humans and animals, followed by AFG1, AFB2 and AFG2, which show lesser toxicity [5]. Generally, 25% of food crops and feed are affected by AFs. AFB1 has carcinogenic, teratogenic, immunosuppressive and hepatotoxic effects and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has classified aflatoxins as a carcinogen (Group 1) [7]. It has been shown that aflatoxins in foodstuff and feed can be decontaminated using different strategies such as physical, chemical and biological methods [8]. Although physical (rinsing, peeling, irradiation,

adsorption and heat treatment) and chemical methods (acid, alkali, ozone and chlorine dioxide treatments) are commonly used, they have some disadvantages such as low efficacy, detrimental effect on important nutrients and high costs [9]. In addition to the mentioned methods, preventive methods can be used to prevent the growth of fungi during harvest or storage. Controlling temperature and humidity during storage is one of the most important factors in preventing the growth of toxigenic fungi [10]. In recent years, biological detoxification has been a promising solution due to the high specificity and efficiency with complete detoxification and without the negative effect on the environment [11]. Therefore, biological decontamination methods using bacteria, fungi, yeasts, enzymes and plants have generated interest among researchers. Probiotic bacteria can also be applied to this object [12]. Studies showed that aflatoxins could bind to bacterial cell walls, including peptidoglycans and polysaccharides, reducing their bioavailability. The binding of aflatoxin to the bacterial wall reduces the binding properties and its lack of accumulation in the intestine, which leads to increased excretion of aflatoxin [12,13,14]. The aim of this review is to discuss the role of probiotics in AF decontamination according to the latest research findings in this area during the period 2019–2024.

1. Probiotics mechanism of action on aflatoxins

Following the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) and the World Health Organisation (WHO), probiotics are live microorganisms with many health

beneficial effects on the host when administered in sufficient amounts [15]. These nonpathogenic microorganisms can be incorporated into many types of products, for instance, foods, dietary supplements and drugs. The most widely studied and used microbial organisms as probiotics are *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Saccharomyces*, *Streptococcus*, *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia* and *Bacillus* [16]. Probiotic bacteria and yeast provide several advantages, such as alleviating symptoms of lactose intolerance, preserving intestinal homeostasis and modulation of immune and inflammatory responses [17]. It is also recognised that probiotic strains bind mycotoxins and decontamination in foods. There are two main mechanisms of action by which AFs can be detoxified biologically: adsorption or binding and degradation [16]. These roles are related to viable and nonviable microorganisms and their cells fragments. Biodegradation is more permanent than the adsorption method, which means that aflatoxin is degraded, and it is impossible to return to the original structure. However, in the absorption method, depending on the affinity of the probiotic to aflatoxin, they may be released over time [7]. After intaking aflatoxins, it is converted to carcinogens metabolites in the liver by cytochrome P450 monooxygenase. These metabolites are produced due to hydroxylation, oxidation and demethylation reactions, and their diversity is very high. The epoxide form of aflatoxin binds to guanine residues in DNA and causes mutations which eventually cause liver cancer. Furan and the lactone ring are two critical sites for the toxicity of aflatoxins [4]. Therefore, any cleavage in the structure of these two rings leads to the detoxification of aflatoxin. Studies have shown that there is the possibility that probiotics can detoxify aflatoxins in two ways. First, aflatoxin can be adsorbed by the wall carbohydrates of probiotics and reduced their bioavailability, and second, the released metabolites of probiotics may degrade aflatoxins. Aflatoxins can bind to peptidoglycans and other cell wall polysaccharides. These noncovalent bonds included van der Waals, electrostatic and hydrogen interactions [18]. In addition to probiotics, postbiotics can also be effective in reducing aflatoxins. Postbiotics include cell-free supernatant (fatty acids, organic acids, enzymes, vitamins and proteins or peptides) and cell wall-derived substances (exopolysaccharide, teichoic acids, peptidoglycans, polar lipids, glycolipids, peptidoglycan and proteins). Since postbiotic compounds are very diverse and the type of bacteria and culture medium are affected by postbiotic compounds, therefore, there is still insufficient evidence as to which compound can interact with aflatoxins. It is possible that postbiotic compounds, especially exopolysaccharides, can interact with aflatoxins and prevent their absorption, which may decrease toxicity [19].

2. Studies overview during the past four years (2019–2024)

Several new studies have exhibited the biodegradation of AFs using probiotics (Table 1.). The potential of some *Lactobacillus* strains to bind AFs has been revealed. For instance, Panwar *et al.* selected eleven tested *Lactobacillus* to remove AFM1 from

phosphate-buffered saline (in 10 ng mL⁻¹ for 6, 12 and 24 h at 37 °C). The results showed that a considerable proportion (4.13% and 64.16%) of AFM1 was removed depending on the incubation period [20]. Some *Lactobacillus* strains also can adsorb AFB1 [21–22]. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* yeasts are also characterised by the ability to adsorb AFB1, with effectiveness ranging from 58% to 97% [22–23] used two probiotic bacteria, *Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus* yoba 2012 and *Streptococcus thermophilus* C106, to decrease aflatoxins B1, B2, G1 and G2. Their finding revealed that *L. rhamnosus* yoba 2012 can decrease all AFs to nondetectable amounts during fermentation. Therefore, several species can be applied together to obtain a special decontamination effect [23–25]. Aflatoxin binding ability depends on the type and concentration of probiotic species, environmental conditions (incubation time and temperature), aflatoxin concentration and the matrix [6,26]. Therefore, these parameters might affect the difference in the aflatoxin removal percent. In the study conducted by Zhang *et al.*, high-temperature and acid treatments enhanced the ability of *L. rhamnosus* LC-4 to bind aflatoxin M1. Bioadsorption should be stable and irreversible, particularly under gastrointestinal conditions [27]. However, in some studies, the adsorbed mycotoxins are released [28]. It has been shown that denatured probiotic and cell-free extracts have more binding effects [29,30,31]. As another aflatoxin detoxification mechanism, biodegradation is irreversible compared to bioadsorption and can convert toxins into low toxicity [27]. Furthermore, a new study showed decontamination of AFB1 through the chemical modifications (dehydrogenation, hydrogenation and hydroxylation) to less or even nontoxic metabolites (Intermediate products with *m/z* of 336.12, 328.13, 166.06, 154.10, 140.08, 116.08 and 82.08) [30]. Pereyra *et al.* reported that *Bacillus* strains could reduce AFB1 to components with less toxicity. They stated that this effect could be related to N-acyl homoserine (AHL) lactonase genes. This enzyme cleaves the ester bond of the AFB1 lactone ring, which is one of the reasons for the toxicity of AFB1 [32]. All studies aforementioned are mainly based on *in vitro* conditions, and there are insufficient published data regarding the actual removal rate of aflatoxin B1 during the transit into the gut (*in vivo*). The first cells exposed to aflatoxins are intestinal cells. Regardless of the species, these cells can absorb aflatoxins at high rates (>80%) [27,32]. It has been established, However, in a gastrointestinal tract simulated model, the gastrointestinal environment positively influences the probiotic cell wall polysaccharide profile and rate of aflatoxin B1 adsorption. Also, it is interesting to note that the AFB1 binding ability *in vivo* decreases compared to the *in vitro* binding ability [12]

3. Possible role of emerging technologies

Our recent publication hypothesized that emerging technologies could enhance the degradation of mycotoxin when combined with bio-approaches such as fermentation [33]. Mycotoxin degradation is possible through the interaction between fermentation and emerging technologies such as ohmic heating,

pulsed electric field, ultrasound, moderate electric fields and high-pressure processing, [30] as these novel techniques can enhance the fermentation process under controlled conditions. The same concept may be applied to probiotics. If an emerging technology can enhance the performance of probiotics or affect their metabolic pathways, this may result in further contributions of these microorganisms to aflatoxin degradation. For example, it was well explained in previous work that ohmic heating and moderate electric fields could positively affect the microorganism's activity under specific treatment conditions [1,32,19]. Future studies may enlighten the possibility of the practical application of such a hypothesis. Such a concept has also been reported in a recent publication for the contribution of ultrasound to brewer yeast fermentation [1,33]. Another publication published a couple of years ago elaborated on the mechanisms involved in microbial activity enhancement through sonication [19]. In addition, some of the emerging technologies, such as ultraviolet radiation (UV) and cold plasma (as it also consists of UV), can induce genetic modifications in probiotics, designing new varieties of probiotics with better performance in aflatoxin degradation. It should be mentioned that converting such ideas to practice needs long-term research, and it is hoped to see that the food industry can take advantage of these potential emerging technologies soon.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that aflatoxins are recognised as a risk to human health, food safety, and economy. While controlling aflatoxins on the farm is preferable to other methods, we must keep in mind that the presence of aflatoxins in the food chain is inevitable. This study showed that probiotics, along with other methods, can be an influential factor in reducing the absorption of aflatoxins. Probiotics decontaminate aflatoxins by binding to their cell wall, including peptidoglycans and polysaccharides, or by degrading their metabolites, such as enzymes. Food matrix, probiotics population, and environmental conditions can significantly affect aflatoxin removal. However, more studies are needed to conclude the detailed mechanisms of aflatoxin degradation and the best conditions for decontamination. It is also hypothesized that emerging technologies alongside probiotics could lead to further reductions in aflatoxins. More studies are needed to identify the best probiotic mix and the optimal colony forming unit (CFU) to maximise aflatoxin reduction.

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